

ISic3699

I.Sicily inscription 3699

Language

Ancient Greek

Type**Material**

marble

Object

tabula

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

2014.09.09

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Acrae

Place of origin (modern)

near Palazzolo Acreide

Provenance

acquired by the museum in 1893

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Paolo Orsi, inventory 12703

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI175589

1. ΑΣΥΡΑΚ Ο
2. ΥΧΑΡΙΣ ΔΙ#⁷
3. Ι ΤΥΧ
- 4.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

PHI 175589

Bibliography

Pugliese Carratelli, G. 1956. Silloge dell' epigrafi acrensi. In Bernabó Brea, L.

(eds.), *Akrai*. Catania. pp. 151-181. At no.73 tav.40

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